

The Rhetoric Of The Poetic Fallacy

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Abstract

The fallacy spread in the Arab culture, and it fluctuated between art, philosophy and logic, and contributed to the creation of culture in its positive character. The poetic formation is a transient understanding of its persistent bias in thought and prose, and on this understanding, a new process is established for the selection of the poem, in which the poet transcends ready-made templates, and replaces them with luring, camouflaging, implication and multiple issues, and then poetry comes out to the area of interest and reading.

Introduction

This approach seeks to investigate the essence of poetic fallacies and their formation when it draws from neighboring fields such as logic, philosophy and rhetoric to carry the research at the boundaries of creativity that fuses with the poet's perceptions in the stages of formulating the poetic text. Ideas gather around the concept of fallacy to demonstrate the breadth of its meanings, fields and representations in the biases of culture, criticism and thought; because "studying fallacies requires invoking several fields, including logic, rhetoric, linguistics and psychology" [1]. The contemplator of the linguistic symbol finds in it a richness of knowledge and wide areas of significance; because "the mistake: other than the injury. It is said: a mistake makes a mistake. The truth of this root is that it stands in contrast to the correctness and meaning that filters when meditating (something that deceives one another) in which the duality of the ego and the other and society is noted [2].

Some scholars have carefully and meticulously directed the concept when they differentiate between error, which is "error and misguidance. If the error occurs in the inference, it is called false or false inference, and it is synonymous with sophistry." The difference between error and fallacy in inference is that the fallacy includes the meaning of Camouflaging the opponent, while the error does not include it" (3), with this understanding this concept attracts with the field of philosophy, which pays great attention to analogy and its fragmentation; Therefore, the "fallacy" was considered a corrupt analogy, either from the side of the image, or from the side of the substance (4) and some of them defined it as "false inference, which has various forms, some of which are real in gender, and some that are real in the chapter, and some of them are general and fall into the rules Definition (5), it borrows some of its procedural tools from philosophical analogy, and reorganizes it in a manner consistent with the forms of inference; That is why the fallacy was defined in the past as "corrupt inference, and the one who comes with it is a fallacy or is mistaken in itself is a fallacy of others. A fallacy with the aim of persuasion"(6), this definition approximates the transformations of the ego and the other, which is a departure from classical rhetoric, that its subject revolves around "approximate, acceptable and probable matters", not matters of fallacy, compulsion, and manipulation of the public's emotions and mind (7). Poetic perceptions remarkably depend on the spirit of fallacy, once it includes the concept of lying and the other is luring and may take its sources from rhetorical or critical fields concerned with reading and receiving, shedding light on the creator and the method of creative formulation. The image of falsehood)) [8], which was mentioned by Abu Hilal Al-Askari (d. 395 A.H.).

The Arabic blogs referred to the concept of fallacy, and its relevance to the fields of Arabic rhetoric as ((a form of fraud and deception)). 637 AH) "This type of speech is one of the sweetest and most subtle of speech because it contains puns, and its reality is that it mentions one of the meanings, which has a likeness in something else and an opposite, and the opposite is better positioned, and a more subtle take"[9]. This is what we can see in the words of Al-Alawi (d. 745 AH), when he spoke about the moral fallacy that "a single word is indicative of two meanings on the side of participation, so they are intended by intention without the utterance because the situation in the common word is that it is indicative of two meanings on the side of substitution. If the two meanings are intended when they are launched, then it is by intent rather than the utterance ... and that the fallacy is only in the common words, and it is indicative of one of them on the side of the substitution and

position. It can be filtered from ideas that affect the recipient, and it is a process whose limits can only be measured in terms of the poet's ingenuity and his ability to link the concept with perception and formulate new concepts, so the fallacy is an inference that amounts to a degree of right," because it is psychologically convincing, not logical, despite what It is an intentional error, in order to hide this error behind linguistic ambiguity or emotional excitement, or to not pay attention to its violation of logical rules. The fallacy draws the concept and the procedure from different fields, which qualifies it to be a technical technique poured by the creator in his work based on the laws of formulation, and the formation of the progress of the work consistent with the thinking of the other. It filters the geometry of the recipient's taste on the one hand, and belief in ideas and values on the other hand, which is the central function of literature.

So it is a fallacy that suggests a deep understanding of creative experiences, just as the logical fallacy in order to be discovered must be learned by its people, the poetic fallacy must be mastered by the poet in order to supplement his poem with artistic shipments that are artistically mature and regulating the means of receiving. Or, the poetic fallacy may be an expressive means that adopts equivocation and pleads with rhetorical methods to formulate a momentary persuasion that disappears with the restoration of inference.

This approach penetrates the core of rhetoric and literary criticism; Because creativity is based on a color of linguistic play that is followed by organizing the inference process to mature ideas and settle in creative awareness, and this perception pulls the poet to search for the intended illusion or distortion in the mold of ideas to rebuild new perceptions that contribute to the synthesis of creative work on the one hand, and its transition to phases. Influential, on the other hand, acknowledges the reader or critic, so he presents the text to reveal its secrets and influences, and since the process of criticism rationally examines the text, the creator and the recipient, there is a dialectic confirming that every rational, calm, sober thinking can turn at any moment and in one way or another into a fallacy A flagrant in which various methods of deception are used, such as Al-Muhajj's intention to tamper his speech with indirect linguistic actions, bringing methods based on force, domination, coercion and threats." , which pulls the fallacy to examine the details of the entire creative process from the ember of the creative work to its new terrain. The fallacy draws the concept and the procedure from different fields, which qualifies it to be a technical technique poured by the creator in his work based on the laws of formulation, and the formation of the progress of the work consistent with the thinking of the other. It filters the geometry of the recipient's taste on the one hand, and belief in ideas and values on the other hand, which is the central function of literature. So it is a fallacy that suggests a deep understanding of creative experiences, just as the logical fallacy in order to be discovered must be learned by its people, the poetic fallacy must be mastered by the poet in order to supplement his poem with artistic shipments that are artistically mature and regulating the means of receiving. Or, the poetic fallacy may be an expressive means that adopts equivocation and pleads with rhetorical methods to formulate a momentary persuasion that disappears with the restoration of inference.

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This is what we can see in the words of Al-Alawi (d. 745 AH), when he spoke about the moral fallacy that "a single word is indicative of two meanings on the side of participation, so they are intended by intention without the utterance because the situation in the common word is that it is indicative of two meanings on the side of substitution. If the two meanings are intended when they are launched, then it is by intent rather than the utterance ... and that the fallacy is only in the common words, and it is indicative of one of them on the side of the substitution and position. It can be filtered from ideas that affect the recipient, and it is a process whose limits can only be measured in terms of the poet's ingenuity and his ability to link the concept with perception and formulate new concepts, so the fallacy is an inference that amounts to a degree of right," because it is psychologically convincing, not logical, despite what It is an intentional error, in order to hide this error behind linguistic ambiguity or emotional excitement, or to not pay attention to its violation of logical rules. The follower of the essence of literary theory finds Aristotle alerted to the poetic fallacy when he detailed the saying about it and its face with analogy and its types. Or the composition, when it was not possible to determine the places of reference in them or the ways in which the words are interconnected within the eloquent and influential saying (15) in the recipient, and these divisions came to contradict the prevailing understanding and derive a new concept that contributes to the formation of the poem; Because "deception or delusion in poetry is unquestioned, and fallacy is a common method among poets and a way to address it in various topics and occasions" (16). Does

poeticism enter into the aesthetic space of language, or does it include other dimensions that are provoked by contemporary approaches? This is exactly what falls within the basic thinking that dismantles the creative and critical text. Therefore, it may be difficult to detect the fallacy on the recipient, but it is clear to the critic at first glance.

So the fallacy is betting on the mental toll that is employed in the context in the sense of the creator's ability to make the fallacy a technique that achieves its purpose and contributes to seizing the semantic dimensions in order to achieve what the horizon of waiting for the interlocutor aims at meaning that it has a field of work in which it moves and liberates from its restrictions to convince and expect the recipient in the temptation of the text Creative because the fallacious coloration does not cease to change its manifestations to turn the truth into a metaphor, and this we find in a rhetorical color in which the "figurative fallacy contributes to creating confusion in the awareness of the recipient in the middle region between the metaphorical and the real signified" (17).

1.2 The rhetoric of fallacy the focus of influence.

This concept is based on a specific focus in which the creator wanders in order to refer the discourse to aesthetic values mixed with the art of camouflage and confusion and dependence on participation in the language and playing on the contents of the discourse. It relies on important techniques to devote this form of expression and ideological thought towards a specific system of concepts. Our probe to achieve this is to organize the limits of the fallacy in another understanding that comes out to the meaning of communication "The fallacy is determined as an argumentative form in order to obstruct the good course of the dialogue. The fallacies violate the rules and standards that are used in communication in general and prevent the interaction from taking place in its correct form"(18). The concept of fallacy is liberated from its logical and persistent concept when it includes a positive dimension that endows poetry with a rank that contributes to the creation process, and for creativity. To fallacy, he gets rid of its dry and strict means to load the literary text with expressive cards charged with its positive power that contribute to the creation of the poem in line with the recipient's perceptions, when he borrows these understandings to present the speech in line with the poet's imagination and his subject.

The language may furnish in its atmosphere a kind of fallacy, which is what its words can perform in terms of derivation, implication, ambiguity and language games that deepen the contents of the saying; Because the poetic itself is based on "methods of confusion and delusion as part of the movement of natural discourse, because if language is of a rhetorical character and rhetoric is linked to the deception found in language, then the use of language is not safe from employing deception and fallacy existing in it"(19), and shifts may charge the text Expression cards on the one hand, and lead to an increase in the meaning, and its breadth, on the other hand, the increase of linguistic energy increases the transcendence of the poetic meanings that are constant in structures and words on the other hand. Considering that the ordinary use of language is not always unambiguous. Unlike in the case in which logical symbols are used, in oral and written communication [many] things remain implicit, it must be strongly emphasized that this does not doubtless mean that the ordinary use of language always includes something from the fallacy in the speech" (20).

Undoubtedly, when the fallacy is transferred to the creative context, we find the artist practicing his fallacies with the tools of fine art, and they permeate literary works with a faint sense that no one may pay attention to; Because it is governed by the context, and this context is needed by the recipient to reveal and liberate the threads of the creative game. Rather, he dismantles them, reveals them, and reproduces them in order to reveal the errors of the creator, and, on the other hand, prove his ingenuity in organizing creative works, and revealing their internal process; This is because this color "takes different forms, so the linguist, for example, resorts to methods, including verbal complexity, by making speech hidden indicative of the intended meaning, or that the words are not arranged according to the order of meanings, or by adopting common and ambiguous words. By means of which their hearts tend to believe the speaker and deny his opponent" (21), the creator may use fallacies to achieve his goal when he is inspired by the data of his work from the manifestations of Arab culture. It is well known that critical approaches paid great attention to the impact on the one hand and the creator on the other hand, and entered the creative creation process in a precise manner. It cannot be neglected from the same context, data that bias the creator and his work on a displacement or playing on the laws of language on the one hand, and his restoration too far types of perceptions to be revealed by the enticement of the recipient and influence By what deception presents on the language is closer to a fallacy, and this perception records the presence of the interpreter, and thus the levels of understanding are present in a remarkable way in this discourse, so a possible interpretation reading is formed from the link between the text and the speaker. Always a conditional character. Because the implicit use of language can be interpreted in different ways depending on the nature of the situation, we cannot speak of a fallacy if the interpretation is categorically justified. In some cases, a breach of a rule of discussion is recognized at once, but at the level of practice it tends to that is until it is an exception and not the rule. Usually, the ruling on the existence or non-existence of a fallacy is a "question of interpretation" (22). The focus of the fallacy may be formed from multiple issues that suggest to the recipient a cognitive cut between the signifier and the signified, so the sign is based on another concept that seeks a new, clear understanding of the sign's informative role and its role that organizes the work,

and presents different manifestations of the reality, and this focus “is generated from the collection of multiple issues in one [then] We present a single answer as if we are dealing with a single issue, and it is defined as a question that includes an implied meaning that the questioner intends to hide in order to deceive the addressee and entrap him... [with him], which makes arguments of this kind a form of fallacy” (23).

This semantic confusion in the duality of the signifier and the signified indicates an important context for the multiplicity of readings, as indicated by Porus, who “extended the scope of the sign to include what is linguistic and what is iconic, and makes semiotic knowledge an appropriate procedural tool for interpretation (24). The creator deposited it in his speech, for the estimate must be based on an accurate understanding of the phenomenon, otherwise, the interpreter may fall into a distant perception, as “a speaker or writer may make a mistake in [using] the knowledge background, or in his assessment of the extent of the expression of the context and the situation alone.” The listener or reader may mistakenly associate the context or situation with the words of the speaker or writer, and thus misinterpret his words” (25).

2. Kaynuna the fallacy in the poetry

These trends cannot be far from the criticism that goes to the effectiveness of the speech and what can be quoted from basic concepts and are always under pressure on the creator. . New where deviation is obtained from the original meaning and is the closest to the concept of flowering.

If the hair is unique and poet and calls for perceptions and employs values and techniques to raise his creative art to the defect and originality to achieve this with creative Mabels, aesthetic values, expression, and outlook. It is known that the fallacy enters various images of the imagination of creative and artistic imagination, and the poetic text "occupies the recipient of the image and the words and the exaggeration and miscellaneousness and misconception and measurement of the mistake. Because they contribute to adopting and submitting creative energies to serve the basis for the basis and organization of molds Creative contribute to the rhythm of the receiver to achieve this creative art, and the poet with his universe and cosmic vision for things calling "that all kinds of implicit things in normal language, or indirectly reflects" (28), and whether the hair is based on many mechanisms The purpose of the delivery, this orientation is overturned and may withdraw the poet to be withdrawn, which is daked on the vigilant of power.

This aspect may not only be limited to other images that the pool of "multiple issues in one question is the answer to the answer provides one response to more than one issue that will inevitably fall in the liquid trap and that salvation is not only retail and individuals (30), and these fallacy are multiple issues "a question that includes a wrong-minded meaning hooks the liquid because this is mammary is a path to the rhythm of the recipient in the trap of fallacy." (31). It is probably a different colors of fallacies that suit the rituals of phenomenon or the place. This models can move in this context and what can be performed because "poetry derives from the exceptional behavior of being all of which he writes our silence all freedom" (33). The noodles will be disposed of compressors passing by the poet, and these perceptions are cleared in the parameters in the hair and maybe there are other patterns of noodles that are not available in this context.

Conclusion

The study concluded to the following results:

1. Tone the fallacy with his desire reader because it depends on the conflict and the greater the absence and its function, and its value, and the means of overtaking the reader and his tee.
2. The mild dimension in literature has limits and features that permeate creative work gaps.
3. The mixing curriculum works on the demolition of work and denying and reinforcement which is the color of the technical disassembly, which destroys the work and stirs its bases and then transmit it towards the erosion and forgetfulness, soon roses a new reading we learned to teach the language of the noodles.
4. Some approaches to the benefit of the noodles as an already speech engineering hair and wearing the dress that awaits the receiver in terms of the tissue and the ignorance and until the ambiguity carried by the features of the fallacy.
5. The hopeful process in the creative process notes the remarkable attendance of all elements of the fallacy and wherever these perceptions found and found the fallacies and cannot be removed from the child's studies, and mild visions and ideas within the text.

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